

FREQUENCY OF BENIGN BLADDER TUMORS

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Relevance. Benign bladder tumors are a very extensive and heterogeneous group of diseases, among which papillomas are prone to recurrence after various periods of time, while relapses are more malignant than previously removed epithelial tumors. The frequency of occurrence of neoplasms of the bladder is about 4-6% of all tumor lesions and 10% of other diseases, the diagnosis and treatment of which is carried out by urology. According to the histological structure of bladder tumors, it is customary to divide them into epithelial and non-epithelial. Most epithelial tumors - up to 98% (90-96% of all bladder tumors are cancer). Benign non-epithelial bladder tumors are extremely rare and are predominantly represented by fibromas, fibromyomas, hemangiomas, leiomyomas, rhabdomyomas, and neurinomas [5, 6, 7]. Both in domestic and foreign literature, reports of such tumors are in the nature of single observations. The most common benign tumor of the bladder, fibroma, occurs only in 0.8% of cases [4, 5].

Benign non-epithelial tumors of the bladder are usually asymptomatic, so they are usually diagnosed incidentally. However, the detection of a bladder tumor requires its morphological verification, which largely determines further treatment tactics.

Purpose of the study: To analyze the biopsy material to study the age-related features of the spread of bladder tumors; to compare the results of preoperative and morphological diagnostics to develop methods for improving treatment.

Materials and research methods. The material for this study was 34 tumor tissue biopsies of patients with benign bladder tumors aged 40 to 65 years who were treated at the Bukhara branch of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Oncology and Radiology in 2021-2022. All histological preparations were made according to the standard method, stained with hematoxylin and eosin, the thickness of the sections was from 5-7 μm and examined using Lake-5 light microscopy.

Research results and discussion. Morphological study was subjected to biopsy specimens of the bladder obtained from 48 patients. According to the results of the study, the following morphological variants of a benign bladder tumor were identified. In 24 men, a bladder polyp was found, the age of the patients ranged from 53 to 67, 7 cases of transitional cell papilloma of the bladder, they had macroscopically 5 cases of which were single nodes ranging in size from 3 to 5 cm; 2 cases of plaque-like shape with uneven surfaces. In 5 patients, recurrent papilloma was found in other parts of the bladder, only 1 case of neoplastic transformation against the background of recurrence of the bladder tumor. Histologically, the removed polyps consisted of crypts covered with a flattened epithelium, edema and cellular inflammatory infiltration were visible in the lamina propria, papillomas had papillary formations, were covered with transitional urothelial epithelium, in one case, urothelial epithelium was found to have neoplastic transformation with transitions to cancer.

Conclusions. Thus, in order to reduce the incidence of bladder tumors, it is necessary to purposefully prevent and adequately treat the above pathological conditions with benign

bladder tumors in the studied material, which allows us to conclude that most of them proceed unnoticed without symptomatic course and are characterized by significant variability. The results of the analysis of morphological studies of micropreparations of different histological variants of the bladder tumor demonstrate a significant degree of uneven distribution of tissue components and structures in different cases of observation. A reliable method for detecting a tumor from its deep sections is transurethral puncture biopsy.

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